

PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF LOW MELTING POINT METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH CONTINUOUS DUCTILE FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

Different types of metallic fibres have been used for reinforcing aluminium-base and zinc-base alloys in order to achieve the best compromise between high temperature strength and fracture toughness. The composites were processed by squeeze casting. The fibres consisted of stainless steel 316L, Inconel 601, or low carbon steel. For Al-based composites, careful control of the solidification rate was required in order to obtain ductile composites devoid of reaction products at interfaces. In zinc-aluminium foundry alloys reinforced with continuous steel fibres, the steady state creep rate decreased when the fibre volume fraction, the fibre diameter, or the preform strength increased.

INTRODUCTION

A drastic enhancement of the creep properties of low melting point alloys can be obtained by reinforcing the alloy with continuous fibres of a more refractory material [1-3]. Alumina, SiC, or carbon fibres may constitute viable solutions. However, the loss of ductility and fracture toughness caused by the presence of brittle fibres may be unacceptable for the mechanical designer. Previous work has shown that, in Zn-based alloys where specific strength is not the issue at stake, reinforcement with metallic fibres offers a good compromise between creep resistance and fracture toughness [4-6]. In contrast, because of the high reactivity of Al with most metals, relatively little attempt has been made up to now to use metallic fibres for reinforcing aluminium alloys. The aim of this paper is twofold. On the one hand, it presents the results of a preliminary investigation showing that proper control of the processing conditions may allow to obtain sound Al-based composites reinforced with metallic fibres. On the other hand, it highlights creep mechanisms in composites constituted of two metallic phases forming interconnected networks.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Three types of metallic fibres have been used in this work : 316L austenitic stainless steel, Inconel 601, and low carbon (0.16%) steel. The 316L and Inconel 601 fibres preforms were manufactured by S.A Bekaert N.V. (trademark Bekipor) by sintering continuous fibres made by bundle drawing. The fibre volume fraction was 20% for 316L and 24% for Inconel 601 and the the average diameter of the fibres was in both cases 12 μ m. Preforms of low carbon steel (LCS) fibres were prepared using the widely commercially available material known as "steel wool" (Pewel). These "fibres" are manufactured by machining continuous turnings from bulk low carbon steel. The shape and size of the cross sections are thus quite irregular. Average equivalent cross section diameters ranging from 13 to 90 μ m are available. The preforms were made by stacking mats of steel wool in such a way as to obtain isotropic planar fibre orientation, by compacting the stacks, and by sintering under protective atmosphere. The composites made with these preforms will be designated by mentioning successively the fibre volume fraction and the average equivalent fibre diameter, e.g. ZA8/LCS-15-15 for ZA8 matrix composites containing 15vol% of 15 μ m diameter low carbon steel fibres.

The composites were processed by squeeze casting under 25 MPa in a cylindrical die of 110mm inner diameter [5-7]. The displacement rate of the punch allowed to induce full infiltration of the preform within less than one second. Care was taken to achieve good thermal contact of the preform against the bottom of the die during infiltration. The extent of interface reaction at fibre/matrix interface is determined by the cooling rate during squeeze casting. In order to optimize the processing conditions, the influence of the cooling rate was studied systematically by varying the thickness of the preform and the mass of the liquid alloy cast in the die, and by setting independently the temperatures of the die, punch, and liquid alloy at the time of casting. (The preform was let to preheat inside the die in such a way as to reach the same temperature as the die). The solidification dwell time on the top surface of the preform was monitored during squeeze casting by means of a thermocouple inserted through the punch. The setup allows to expel the casting from the die and to quench it in water as soon as possible after completion of solidification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

AL-BASED MATRIX COMPOSITES

Fig. 1 illustrates the influence of processing conditions on the microstructure of composites of 99.99% pure Al matrix reinforced with 20 vol% 316L fibres. The micrograph of Fig1.a shows the effect of a too slow cooling rate. It was obtained in the central part of a composite made according to the following conditions : preform thickness 10mm ; die temperature 250°C ; casting temperature 800°C ; mass of liquid 450g. The solidification dwell time was about 4s, which was sufficiently high as to induce extensive formation of intermetallic compounds. In contrast, the micrograph of Fig 1.b is typical of a properly processed composite. The conditions were as follows : preform thickness 1mm ; die temperature 25°C ; casting temperature 750°C ; mass of liquid 225g. The corresponding solidification dwell time was lower than 1s. Very little intermetallic precipitates can be seen along the fibre/matrix interfaces, although the presence of some interdendritic eutectic phase attests that some dissolution of the fibres has occurred.

Figure 1. Micrographs of 99.99% Al/316L composites processed under different conditions : (a) preform thickness 10mm ; die temperature 250°C ; casting temperature 800°C ; mass of liquid 450g. (b) preform thickness 1mm ; die temperature 25°C ; casting temperature 750°C ; mass of liquid 225g.

Optimization of processing conditions aimed at providing the highest possible cooling rate without impairing full infiltration of the preform. The most important parameters are the die temperature, the mass of the alloy, the preform temperature, and the preform volume fraction. Optimized conditions have been searched for pure Al matrix composites reinforced with 1mm thick preforms of 20 vol% 316L fibres and 1.5 mm thick preforms of 24vol% Inconel 601 fibres. For the best conditions achieved to date, Fig. 2 compares typical tensile stress-strain curves of these two composites with the curves of the 99.99% pure Al matrix and of a composite Al/316L containing large amounts of intermetallic compounds (such as in Fig. 1.a). The latter composite exhibited no ductility. The average values of the 0.2% yield strength, $\sigma_{0,2\%}$, ultimate tensile strength, σ_u , and strain at fracture, ϵ_f , are given in Table 1. The large ductility obtained for composites Al/Inconel 601 is quite remarkable. In contrast, the processing conditions used for composites Al/316L do not allow to obtain performances comparable to that of composites Al/Inconel. Observation of the fracture surfaces by SEM gives evidence of a larger fibre pull-out length in the former composite than in the latter, which indicates a lower interface adhesion or a more brittle interface. This difference suggests that the processing conditions of composites Al/316L can still be improved in order to achieve better tuning of interface properties.

Table 1 Mechanical properties

	$\sigma_{0,2\%}$ (MPa)	σ_u (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)
Al/20% 316L (9 specimens)	73 ± 12	79 ± 16	1.4 ± 1.1
Al/24% Inconel 601 (10 specimens)	135 ± 10	188 ± 14	4.6 ± 1.4

An alternative method for controlling interface reactivity is by alloying the matrix [7]. As an example, figure 3 presents the microstructure of a composite made by infiltrating alloy AS13

(whose composition is close to the eutectic Al-Si) into a preform of 316L fibres using the following squeeze casting conditions : preform thickness 10mm ; die temperature 250°C ; casting temperature 850°C ; mass of liquid 380g. Although these conditions induce a slow cooling rate, no reaction compound is formed in this composite. Indeed, Si is known to reduce drastically the reactivity of liquid Al with steel [8]. Work in progress is aiming at using steel fibre preforms for reinforcing locally pressure die cast Al-Si foundry alloys in order to improve strength at elevated temperature.

Figure 2. Comparison of typical stress-strain curves for properly processed composites Al/316L and Al/Inconel 601 with the curves of the 99.99% pure Al matrix and of a composite Al/316L containing large amounts of intermetallic compounds.

Figure 3. Absence of interfacial reaction in composite AS13/316L processed using the following conditions : preform thickness 10mm ; die temperature 250°C ; casting temperature 850°C ; mass of liquid 380g.

ZINC-BASED MATRIX COMPOSITES

The creep strength of zinc-aluminium foundry alloys can be drastically improved by reinforcing the alloy with steel fibres [4-6]. As a model of this type of composite, we have studied extensively the reinforcement of alloy ZA8 whose nominal composition is (8-8.8)wt% Al, (0.8-1.3)wt% Cu, (0.015-0.03)wt% Mg, balance Zn. The composites were processed by squeeze casting using the following conditions : preform thickness 10mm ; die temperature 300°C ; casting temperature 560°C ; mass of liquid 830g. The reactivity of liquid ZA8 with steel fibres being much lower than that of Al-based alloys, no reaction product could be detected at fibre/matrix interfaces even in the case of low carbon steel fibres. As the price of these fibres is more compatible with the price of alloy ZA8, our recent work has concentrated on the investigation of the creep strengthening induced by preforms of low carbon steel fibres. The random planar orientation of the fibres in the composites is illustrated in Fig.4 for composite ZA8/LCS-15-15.

Figure 4 Illustration of random planar orientation of the fibres in composites ZA8/LCS-15-15

Figure 5. Variation of the steady state creep rate at 150°C (423K) under 40MPa for composites ZA8/LCS as a function of the equivalent fibre diameter and fibre volume fraction

A particular feature of composites ZA8/LCS is that they allow to study creep mechanisms at a conveniently low temperature (100-150°C). They constitute thus a model system for the investigation of creep mechanisms in composites. A systematic investigation was made of the influence of fibre volume fraction, fibre diameter, stress, and temperature on the stationary creep rate of composites ZA8/LCS. Fig. 5 summarizes the results obtained at 150°C (423K) under 40MPa. For a given fibre volume fraction, the stationary creep rate appears to increase roughly exponentially with increasing average fibre diameter. This "size effect" cannot be accounted for on the basis of continuum mechanics models.

Measurement of stationary creep rate as a function of temperature allowed to determine the activation energy for creep in composites ZA8/LCS. Whatever the fibre volume fraction and the fibre diameter, the activation energy remained fairly close to 110 kJmol⁻¹, i.e. close to the activation energy for diffusion in Zn. This indicates that the creep rate is solely governed by the creep rate of the matrix. The low creep rate appears thus to result from the effect of the load transfer from the matrix to the fibres.

It is tempting to attempt to evaluate the stress carried out by the fibres by measuring the anelastic strain recovery recorded when unloading the specimen during creep testing. A typical example is shown in Fig. 6 for composite ZA8/LCS-15-15 creeping under 40MPa at 150°C. The strain recovery amounts to 0.4%. Such a high value cannot be justified by taking account of the Young's modulus of the individual fibres as it would correspond to a stress of 800 MPa, which largely exceeds the tensile strength of low carbon steel fibres. This indicates that one has to consider that the stress is transferred not to the individual fibres but to the whole interconnected network of fibres behaving as a continuous phase [9].

Figure 6. Example of anelastic strain recovery in composite ZA8/LCS-15-15 unloaded during creep testing at 150°C (423K) under 40MPa

This suggests that the dependence of the creep rate on the fibre diameter could be ascribed to a dependence of the preform strength on fibre diameter. This is confirmed by Fig.7 which shows the influence of fibre diameter on the tensile stress strain curves of preforms of 15vol% of low carbon steel fibres prepared by sintering at 800°C for 4h. The larger the equivalent fibre diameter, the lower the preform strength. Indeed, the maximum load which can be carried by the bonds formed at fibre crossings during sintering should depend only on the sintering

conditions whereas, when loading the interconnected network of fibres, the load to be supported by each of these bonds scales as the inverse of the fibre diameter.

Fig.7 indicates that the preforms of low carbon steel fibres present a very low strength. This strength is also quite anisotropic : the preform strength in the direction perpendicular to the plane of the fibres could not be measured but is certainly even much lower than the in-plane strength. The preform should thus flow plastically at a rate determined by the creep rate of the matrix. However, tensile testing of the preform does not allow to predict the flow stress supported by the preform in the composite as the preform strength is certainly enhanced by the constraint of the matrix. The elucidation of the creep behaviour of these composites thus requires a proper modelling of this constraint effect on the strength of the preform. This modelling should be validated by in situ measurements of the stress in the fibre network.

Figure 7. Influence of equivalent fibre diameter on the tensile stress-strain curves of preforms of 15vol% of low carbon steel fibres

CONCLUSIONS

This work highlights some of the prospects offered by the use of ductile fibres in metallic composites. Squeeze casting with high solidification rates makes possible the engineering of adequate interfacial properties in Al matrix composites reinforced with metallic fibres. The investigation of the creep behaviour of Zn matrix composites allows to elucidate creep mechanisms governing the properties of metallic composites at elevated temperature.

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REFERENCES

1. A. Kelly, and K.N. Street, Creep of discontinuous fibre composites-II. Theory for the steady state, *Proc. Roy. Soc. London, Ser.A* 328 (1972) 283
2. H. Lilholt, Relation between matrix and composite creep behaviour in "Fatigue and creep of composite materials" (H. Lilholt and R.Talreja, eds). Risø National Laboratory, Roskilde, Denmark, 1982, p.63.
3. T.G. Nieh, Creep rupture of a silicon carbide reinforced aluminium composite, *Metall. Trans. A*, 15A (1984) 139 - 146
4. F. Delannay, C. Colin, Y. Marchal, L. Tao, F. Boland, P. Cobzaru, B. Lips, and M-A. Dellis, Processing and properties of metal matrix composites reinforced with continuous fibres for the control of thermal expansion, creep resistance and fracture toughness *Journal de Physique, Colloque C7, Vol 3* (1993) 1675
5. F. Delannay, L. Tao, F. Boland and J. Wégria, Processing and properties of zinc-aluminium matrix composites reinforced with steel fibres, in "Advances in Science, Technology and Applications of Zn-Al Alloys" Edited by G. Torres Villaseñor, Y.H. Zhu and C. Pina, UNAM, Mexico, 1994, pp 151 - 156
6. L. Tao, M-A. Dellis, F. Boland, J. Wégria and F. Delannay, Comparison of fibres for the creep strengthening of zinc-aluminium foundry alloys, *Composites, in press*
7. C. Colin, Y. Marchal, F. Boland, and F. Delannay, Stainless steel fibres reinforced aluminium matrix composites processed by squeeze casting : relationship between processing conditions and interface microstructure, *Journal de Physique IV, Colloque C7, Vol 3, (1993), pp 1749-1752*
8. R.W Richards, D.D. Jones, P.D. Clements, and H. Clarke, Metallurgy of continuous hot dip aluminising, *International Materials Reviews* (1994) pp 191-212
9. T.L. Dragone, and W.D. Nix, Steady state and transient creep properties of an aluminum alloy reinforced with alumina fibres, *Acta metall. mater.*, Vol.40 , No. 10 (1992) 2781-2791